

Studies in 1-Aza-1, 3-butadienes : Preparation of Secondary Amines from Conjugated Azomethines

NAZAR SINGH and KEWAL KRISHAN

Department of Chemistry, Punjab University, Patiala

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Secondary amines have been obtained in quantitative yields by the reduction of conjugated azomethines with sodium borohydride at 50°-60° without affecting the conjugated nitro and CH = CH (trans) groups. The UV, IR, NMR and high resolution mass spectra are also given.

FOR the preparation of secondary amines from azomethines various methods of reduction like catalytic and electrolytic reduction, metal reduction systems, diborane and metal hydrides have been described¹. Secondary amines have been successfully prepared in these laboratories² by reduction of conjugated imines with lithium borohydride and sodium borohydride under relatively milder conditions. The effect of substituents in the cinnamic aldehyde moiety on the course of this reaction of these conjugated imines has not yet been reported. A number of substituted N-*o*-nitrocinnamalidines have been synthesized³ by condensing pure *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde with substituted aromatic amines. *o*-Nitrocinnamaldehyde⁴ was obtained by the nitration of freshly distilled cinnamaldehyde in acetic anhydride (BDH) using nitric acid (AR) in glacial acetic acid (BDH) as the nitrating agent of 0°-5°.

Effects of conjugation with strong electrophilic nitro group in the ortho position of the cinnamaldehyde ring of the molecule, on the reduction of these conjugated azomethines with sodium borohydride have been studied. Sodium borohydride has been found to be an excellent selective reducing

agent as it did not affect the conjugated carbon-carbon double bond and the nitro group under the reaction conditions employed. It has been observed that the reaction failed to occur under the milder conditions described earlier². More strenuous conditions *i.e.*, refluxing temperatures, use of sodium hydroxide and longer reaction periods, had to be employed to effect successful reduction. However, the forcing reaction conditions were partly necessitated because of the low solubility of the 1-aza-1, 3-butadienes. The conjugation of the azomethine function with an electrophilic nitro group seems mainly responsible for this deactivation. Substituents in the amine moiety of the molecule also seem to influence the reaction. The presence of a methyl function in the

ortho position of the aniline unit totally suppressed the reaction. This is perhaps due to the steric hindrance caused by the presence of the bulky ortho methyl group in the vicinity of the azomethine linkage. Further, the reduction was not possible when the substituent was a hydroxyl in the ortho

or para position of the aniline ring of the molecule and under the reaction conditions, intense colour changes from yellowish-brown to blood-red were observed in the case of these compounds. This may be due to the quinonoid forms of the molecules assisted by the nitro group conjugation. The reduction products of anils from aniline, *p*-toluidine and *p*-anisidine were obtained as thick oils, that could neither be purified, nor could they yield picrates, primarily due to easy resinification to black tar-like materials. It may be noted that the corresponding cinnamylidene anilines could be reduced easily in high yields³.

The crystalline secondary amines derived from the reduction of these azomethines have been characterized by their elemental analysis, UV, IR, NMR and mass spectra. A study of these spectra in conjugation with those of the parent 1-aza-1, 3-butadienes^{3,5} reveals that the absorption bands, assigned to azomethine linkage (-CH = N-), are absent in the spectra of these secondary amines. The absorption maxima (~280 mμ) disappears completely in the UV spectra and the absorption bands (~1610 cm⁻¹) in the IR spectra assigned to the C=N group, are also absent. Instead additional bands (3438-3420 cm⁻¹) assigned to N-H frequency are present, as expected. The nitro group frequencies between 1524-1508 and 1350-1332 cm⁻¹ and -CH = CH- (trans) absorptions between 972-958 cm⁻¹, remain unaffected. The 100 MHz-NMR spectra of the secondary amine obtained by the reduction of 1-*p*-ethoxyphenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-

1,3-butadiene has also been recorded. The assignment of the signal of the proton H_D is confirmed,

$\delta_{TMS}^{CDCl_3} \tau$ 2.14, d(H_A); 3.7, sextet (H_B); 6.63, s(H_D)

as this signal disappears after deuterium exchange with D_2O . The high resolution mass spectrum of this compound indicates that the molecular ion peak (m/e 298) is the base peak.

Experimental

Preparation of Secondary Amines by the Reduction of 1-Aza-1,3-butadienes with Sodium Borohydride: A typical method is described below for the reduction of 1-*p*-ethoxyphenyl-4-*o*-nitrophenyl-1-aza-1,3-butadiene.

In a three necked 250 ml., R.B. flask fitted with a mechanical stirrer, a thermometer and a dropping funnel was placed a solution of the azabutadiene (2.96 g., 0.01 mole, in 50 ml. methanol) and sodium borohydride (2.0 g. in 2 ml. of 2*N* sodium hydroxide diluted to 20 ml. with water) was added to it from

the dropping funnel at the rate of 0.5 ml. per minute, with continuous stirring and throughout the operation the temperature was maintained at 50°-55°. When about three quarters of sodium borohydride solution had been added, a turbidity began to appear, followed by the deposition of some solid. After the addition was complete, the reaction mixture was stirred for one hour more at room temperature and then allowed to stand overnight. Excess of the solvent was then pulled off in vacuo on a steam-bath. The reaction mixture was then diluted with water and chilled in an ice-bath. The crude product was filtered at the pump and was recrystallized from ethanol to give orange needles, m.p. 65°, 2.98 g. (100% yield). (Found : N, 9.23; Calc. for $C_{17}H_{18}N_2O_3$: N, 9.39). ν_{max}^{KBr} (cm^{-1}) 3420 (N-H); 1509, 1337, s(NO_2) and 958, m (CH = CH, trans). 100 MHz $\delta_{TMS}^{CDCl_3} \tau$ 6.63, s(N- H_D).

High Resolution Mass Spectrum: Molecular ion peak at m/e 298 is the base peak. Other prominent peaks are at m/e 211, 162, 136, 117, 116, 109, 108.

The characteristics of other secondary amines, which have been similarly obtained are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1

S.No.	X =	Physical Appearance	M.P.* °C	Yield %	Solvent of Recrystallisation	Mol. Formula	Elemental Analysis	
							Found N%	Calc. N%
1.	<i>p</i> -OEt	small orange needles	65	100	95% Ethanol	$C_{17}H_{18}N_2O_3$	9.23	9.39
2.	<i>m</i> -Cl	shining yellow needles	62	-do-	-do-	$C_{15}H_{13}N_2O_2Cl$	9.50	9.70
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl	long, bright orange needles	78	-do-	Methanol	$C_{15}H_{13}N_2O_2Cl$	9.59	9.70
4.	<i>p</i> -Br	fine, yellow needles	69-70	-do-	Solvent ether	$C_{15}H_{13}N_2O_2Br$	8.20	8.40
5.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	shining red needles	134-135	-do-	Glacial Acetic Acid	$C_{15}H_{13}N_2O_4$	14.08	14.24
6.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	fine, yellow needles	140-141	-do-	-do-	$C_{15}H_{13}N_2O_4$	14.30	14.24

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

TABLE 2

S.N.	X =	Ultraviolet Spectra			Infrared Spectra (cm^{-1})					
		Band I		Band II		N-H	NO ₂	CH = CH trans		
		MeOH λ max($m\mu$)	(log ϵ)	MeOH λ max($m\mu$)	(log ϵ)				MeOH λ max($m\mu$)	(log ϵ)
1.	<i>p</i> -OEt	207.5	(4.55)	242.5	(4.59)	310.0	(4.04)	3420, s	1509, vs 1337, s	958, m
2.	<i>m</i> -Cl	—	—	—	—	—	—	3380, m	1510, s 1340, s	975, s 960, s
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl	209.0	(3.76)	252.5	(3.86)	309.5	(3.07)	3400, s	1512, vs 1343, vs	992, m 968, m
4.	<i>p</i> -Br	209.0	(4.40)	254.0	(4.44)	310.0	(3.87)	3400, s	1508, vs 1340, vs	966, m
5.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	209.0	(4.39)	242.5	(4.67)	—	—	3390, m	1520, s 1510, s	985, s 960, s
6.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	209.5	(4.2967)	235.5	(4.36)	382.5	(4.33)	3338, s	1372, s 1524, vs 1350, s	968, m 980, m

The UV spectra have been recorded on a manually operated UV spectrophotometer (Hilger-Watts Model H-700) in methanol (BDH) using silica cells. The IR spectra have been recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer as KBr discs.

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